

Analysis of Padang Development Potential Creative City Based on Sustainable Environment through Multistakeholder Perception (Hexa Helix)

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Abstract:- The development of creative cities is expected to encourage equitable distribution of regional development through the acceleration of economic growth centers by exploring the city's superior potentials. As an area that has various creative potentials, the city of Padang needs to continue to improve and be prepared to support the realization of a sustainable creative city. This study aims to analyze the development potential of Padang as a creative city based on multi-stakeholder perceptions (hexa helix), especially the government as policy makers in encouraging the development of a sustainable environment-based creative city and analyze the potential for developing a sustainable environmentally-based creative city Padang through multi-stakeholder perceptions (hexa helix). The results show that the city of Padang has various potentials that can encourage the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment through multi-stakeholder synergy (hexa helix).

Keywords:- Creative City, Sustainable Environment, Multistakeholder.

I. INTRODUCTION

Urbanization has spurred rapid urban population growth in West Sumatra. Many residents outside the city migrate to the city of Padang because activities and activities in all aspects of the field are development goals. This happens because it is supported by the ease of access and migration of residents to the city of Padang which has a positive impact from various aspects, ranging from environmental sustainability, social sustainability and economic growth. Key Statistical Data for the City of Padang (2020) reports that the population reaches 909,040 people spread over 11 sub-districts and 104 urban villages with economic growth reaching 5.65% in 2019 and falling to -1.86% in 2020 due to the pandemic. This also has an impact on the labor force and investment, economic growth and the human development index, population growth and public concern for environmental sustainability.

The environment plays an important role in the life of living things, especially humans as social beings. Environmental elements consist of abiotic, biotic and socio-cultural elements. According to Dewata and Danhas (2018), environmental science is a multidisciplinary field. As an academic field, environmental science integrates physics, biology, chemistry, ecology, soil science, geology,

atmospheric science, and geography to study the environment and find solutions to existing environmental problems. In principle, environmental science examines everything related to environmental problems, including environmental change, preservation of environmental functions and environmental management.

Based on data from the Environment Indonesia Center (2020), there are ten major environmental problems in Indonesia, namely: 40% waste, 20% flooding, 11% polluted rivers, 10% global warming, 6% air pollution, 4% damage to marine ecosystems, 3% difficulty clean water, 2% forest destruction, 2% abrasion, and 2% soil pollution. This is closely related to environmental sustainability, social sustainability and also has an impact on economic growth in a city. The environment has an important meaning as a supporter and supporter for the life of living things. Active participation of city residents and supported by the government, the above problems can be solved properly.

The definition of creative city is still very diverse. Some understand the creative city with the crafts that are owned in its area, others identify it with a region. A common understanding on the diversity of these definitions is very much needed as a basis for obtaining the ideal creative city development concept, so that it can be used as an alternative economic driving force and solution for contextual problems according to the character and dynamics in Indonesia.

Based on UNCTAD (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development) (2010), there are four ways to simplify the notion of a creative city, namely: 1). creative city as art and cultural infrastructure, 2). creative city as a creative economy, 3). creative city as a synonym for strong creative class, and 4). a creative city that fosters a culture of creativity.

The development of creative cities is expected to encourage equitable regional development by accelerating the development of economic growth centers by exploring regional potentials and advantages. This expectation is in line with the 11th goal of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) initiated by UNDP, which is to create an inclusive, safe, comfortable and sustainable city. The creative city concept developed by UCCN requires multi-stakeholder synergy between stakeholders, to make this happen, the city of Padang must have a clear DNA with a structured development model.

In 2012, the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy encouraged five cities: Solo, Bandung, Denpasar, Yogyakarta, and Pekalongan to submit applications as part of efforts to join UCCN (UNESCO Creative Cities Network). Of the five cities, only Pekalongan was accepted as a member in 2014 in the fields of crafts and folk arts. The following year (2015), the city of Bandung was also accepted as a member of UCCN in the field of design. In 2019, the city of Ambon was accepted as a member of UCCN in the field of music. Then in 2021, the city of Jakarta was accepted as a member of UCCN in the field of literacy (ICCN, 2017).

As a city that has various creative potentials, the City of Padang needs to continue to improve and be prepared to support the realization of sustainability through a creative city. For this reason, it is necessary to explore the existing local potential, and support from multistakeholders for the development of the city of Padang as a creative city based on a sustainable environment. Multistakeholders in a creative city are known as the hexa helix which consists of six elements (Academic, Business, Community, Government, Media & Aggregator), namely academics, business, community (society), government, media and aggregators. According to the results of a study by Satari and Larasati (2021), multi-stakeholder synergy plays a very important role in supporting the sustainability and development of creative cities. Based on the description above, this study aims to determine the potential for the development of Padang as a creative city based on a sustainable environment based on multi-stakeholder perceptions (hexa helix).

II. RESEARCH METHODS

Respondents in this study were multistake holders (hexa helix) who were involved in efforts to develop Padang as a creative city based on a sustainable environment. In this study, multistakeholder is limited to top level management or related to policy making and determining the strategy of developing a creative city based on a sustainable environment. In detail, the respondents in this study amounted to 52 people who were selected by purposive sampling (Barlian, 2016) from academia, business, community, government, media and aggregators in the city of Padang.

Sources of data obtained from primary data and secondary data. Data was collected through the distribution of online questionnaires, discussions, interviews, observations and documentation. The data obtained in this study, among others, contain demographic data based on gender, age, profession, work experience and recent education as well as respondents' responses to various things through closed questions related to the potential for developing a creative city based on a sustainable environment in Padang.

This research is a descriptive study because it aims to make a systematic, factual, and accurate picture or painting of the facts, characteristics and relationships between phenomena regarding the efforts to develop a creative city

based on a sustainable environment in the city of Padang. This research is both quantitative and qualitative research. Quantitatively, the data will be analyzed using descriptive statistics and qualitatively the data analysis will be carried out by reducing data, presenting data, and drawing conclusions. In addition, content analysis and summary analysis were also carried out.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained from the answers of 52 respondents who were willing to fill out and return the questionnaire, obtained various information describing the demographic characteristics of the respondents and their perceptions related to the research topic. Respondents come from multistake holders (hexa helix) at the top level management or related to policy making, including: academics, business, community, government, media and aggregators in the city of Padang.

The following presents data on the characteristics of respondents based on gender, age, profession, work experience and recent education.

No	Gender	Amount (People)	Percentage (%)
1	Male	29	55,77
2	Woman	23	44,23
		52	100

Table 1: Characteristics of Respondents by Gender

Based on table 1, it is known that the number of male respondents is more than female respondents. Of the 52 respondents, 29 people (55.77 percent) were male and 23 (44.23 percent) were female.

Characteristics of respondents based on age can be seen in table 2 as follows:

No	Age	Amount (People)	Percentage (%)
1	20-30 Years	5	9,61
2	30-40 Years	16	30,77
3	41-50 Years	19	36,54
4	>50 Years	12	23,08
		52	100

Table 2: Characteristics of Respondents by Type of Age

Respondents in this study were in the productive age range from various multi-stakeholder representatives (hexa helix) in the city of Padang. The youngest age of the respondent is 20 years old and the highest age of the respondent is 50 years old. Based on table 2, it is known that the age of respondents under 20-30 years is 9.62 percent and is the smallest age group of respondents. Respondents in the age group range of 41-50 years were the most respondents with a total of 19 people (36.54 percent), the group of respondents aged 30-40 years was 30.77 percent, the group of respondents aged > 50 years was 23.08 percent. Respondents in this study were top level management/leadership and chairman so that in general

they have had a long service period and are in a higher age group.

Characteristics of respondents by profession can be seen in table 3 as follows:

No	Profession	Amount (People)	Percentage (%)
1	Academics	10	19,22
2	Business	24	46,15
3	Community	5	9,62
4	Government	9	17,31
5	Media	2	3,85
6	Aggregator	2	3,85
		52	100

Table 3: Characteristics of Respondents by Profession

Based on table 3, it is known that the largest number of respondents came from business circles as many as 24 people (46.15 percent). Respondents with the least number of respondents came from the media and aggregators with the same number of 2 people each (3.85 percent). Furthermore, there were 10 respondents from academia (19.22 percent). Respondents from the government were 9 people (17.31 percent). Respondents from the community were 5 people (9.62 percent).

Characteristics of respondents by profession can be seen in table 4 as follows:

No	Work Experience	Amount (People)	Percentage (%)
1	1-5 Years	14	26,93
2	6-10 Years	7	13,46
3	11-15 Years	7	13,46
4	16-20 Years	7	13,46
5	>20 Years	17	32,69
		52	100

Table 4: Characteristics of Respondents Based on Work Experience

The majority of respondents who have work experience for > 20 years are 17 people (32.69 percent). In a row, there are 14 respondents who have work experience for 1-5 years (26.93 percent). Respondents who have work experience for 6-10 years, 11-15 years, 16-20 years with the same number of 7 people each (13.46 percent).

Characteristics of respondents based on the last education can be seen in table 5 as follows:

No	Education	Amount (People)	Percentage (%)
1	Senior High School	3	5,76
2	Diploma	2	3,85
3	Bachelor	23	44,23
4	Master	19	36,54
5	Doctoral	5	9,62
		52	100

Table 5: Characteristics of Respondents Based on Last Education

The majority of respondents have a strata 1 (S1) educational background with a total of 23 people (44.23 percent). In succession, 19 people (36.54 percent) have a strata 2 (S2) education level, 5 people (9.62 percent) have a high school education level/equivalent (5 .76 percent) and the least respondents are those who have a diploma educational background as many as 2 people (3.85 percent).

To find out the multi-stakeholder perception of the potential development of Padang as a creative city based on a sustainable environment, it can be seen from the results of the analysis of respondents' answers to closed questions that influence each other and are given through online questionnaires. The discussion is also equipped with a qualitative analysis based on observations and interviews with selected respondents. In this study, respondents were asked to provide answers to eight closed questions related to creative cities :

Question: Can human resources influence the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment?

Y1	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
3	2	3.85	3.85
4	16	30.77	34.62
5	34	65.38	100.00

Total	52	100.00	

Table 6: Respondents' Answers to the First Closed Question

The answer to the first closed question shows that most respondents know that human resources can influence the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment with a very influential answer as many as 34 people (65.38 percent). In general, these human resources have been known by the respondents and have often been heard of. However, socialization regarding the influence of human resources needs to be maximized, so that respondents' understanding is still limited to terms.

Question: Can digital (ICT) and physical infrastructure affect the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment?

Y3	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
3	2	3.85	3.85
4	21	40.38	44.23
5	29	55.77	100.00

Total	52	100.00	

Table 7: Respondents' Answers to the Third Closed Question

The answers to the third closed question show that most of the respondents know that digital (ICT) and physical infrastructure can affect the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment with 29 people (55.77 percent) very influential answers.

Question: Can the excellent potential affect the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment?

Y5	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
4	10	19.23	19.23
5	42	80.77	100.00

Total	52	100.00	

Table 8: Respondents' Answers to the Fifth Closed Question

The answer to the fifth closed question shows that most of the respondents know that superior potential can influence the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment with a very influential answer as many as 42 people (80.77 percent).

Question: Can the maintenance and development of creative economy potential affect the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment?

Y8	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
4	10	19.23	19.23
5	42	80.77	100.00

Total	52	100.00	

Table 9: Respondents' Answers to Closed Questions Eight

The answers to the eight closed questions showed that most of the respondents knew that the maintenance and development of creative economy potential could affect the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment with 42 people (80.77 percent) very influential answers.

Question: Can the maintenance of creative classes (creative groups/individuals) affect the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment?

Y9	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
3	2	3.85	3.85
4	22	42.31	46.15
5	28	53.85	100.00

Total	52	100.00	

Table 10: Respondents' Answers to Closed Questions Nine

The answers to the eight closed questions indicate that the maintenance of creative classes (creative groups/individuals) can influence the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment with a very influential answer as many as 28 people (53.85 percent).

Question: Can the planning and development of a creative environment affect the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment?

Y10	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
3	1	1.92	1.92
4	16	30.77	32.69
5	35	67.31	100.00

Total	52	100.00	

Table 11: Respondents' Answers to Ten Closed Questions

The answers to the eight closed questions indicate that the planning and development of a creative environment can influence the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment with a very influential answer as many as 35 people (67.31 percent).

Furthermore, closed questions are presented that ask about the potential for developing a creative city based on a sustainable environment in Padang. The development potential in Padang City is grouped into the following indicators:

Y1: Can human resources influence the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment?

Y2 : Can creative space affect the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment?

Y3 : Can digital and physical infrastructure (ICT) affect the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment?

Y4: Can synergy and collaboration between stakeholders affect the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment?

Y5: Can excellent potential affect the development of a sustainable environment-based creative city?

Y8: Can the maintenance and development of creative economy potential affect the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment?

Y9 : Can the maintenance of creative classes (creative groups/individuals) affect the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment?

Y10: Can creative environmental planning and development affect the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment?

Fig. 1: Measurement Model of PLS-SEM Analysis with STATA Source: Satria, Haris (2022)

Based on the results of the PLS-SEM analysis study with STATA, it shows that the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment is influenced by: human resources, creative space, digital and physical infrastructure, synergy and collaboration between stakeholders, excellent potential, maintenance and development of economic potential creative, creative class maintenance (group/individual), creative environment planning and development. This shows that efforts towards developing Padang as a creative city based on a sustainable environment require government support as well as cooperation and coordination through multi-stakeholder synergy (helix).

IV. CONCLUSION

The results show that the city of Padang has various potentials that can encourage the development of a creative city based on a sustainable environment through multi-stakeholder synergy (hexa helix). This is supported by various things, both in the form of support from human resources and government policies as well as from the creative potential that exists in the community. As an effort to develop Padang as a creative city based on a sustainable environment, the government as the main stakeholder needs to develop strategies and policies in relevant models. The results of the potential analysis can be used as a reference in designing a creative city development model based on a sustainable environment.

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B. Identify the Headings

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